

1580 cm^{-1} we observe a lowering of 50 cm^{-1} . A sharp aromatic C-C stretch is observed at 1480 cm^{-1} due to the tetraphenyl boron anion. The carbonyl stretch (C=O) in the complex remains almost unchanged at 1630 cm^{-1} compared to that in the free carbohydrazide (1635 cm^{-1}). This small variation cannot be taken as an indication of its coordination to nickel(II). A critical study of the i.r. spectra of the three compounds (I, II, III) thus reveals that nickel(II) is coordinated to the macrocyclic ligand through its four C=N groups.

B. Conductivity :

In nitromethane, (.001 molar solution), the complex registers a value of 129 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ which is quite good for a bi-univalent electrolyte with a heavy anion like tetraphenyl boron¹⁶.

C. Electronic spectra and Magnetic properties :

The macrocyclic complex crystallises with two molecules of water which could be removed at 120°. The anhydrous sample shows only one spectral band in the solid state at about 390 nm (25.6kK) which is indicative of a square planar [NiN₄] chromophore^{17,18}. The anhydrous sample was found to be diamagnetic. Interestingly, the hydrated complex shows a paramagnetic moment of 1.5 B.M. and its electronic spectrum is not well resolved. The solid crystalline hydrated complex probably indicates an equilibrium between the square planar dihydrate and pseudo-octahedral diaquo complex.

References

1. G. A. MELSON and D. H. BUSCH, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 223.
2. D. CURRY and D. H. BUSCH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 592.
3. J. CHRISTENSEN and D. J. EATOUGH and M. IZATT, *Chem. Revs.*, 1974, **74**, 351.
4. A. KALLIGEROS and E. L. BLINN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 1145.
5. W. ROSEN and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 262.
6. A. C. L. SU and J. E. WAIHER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 176.
7. E. L. BLINN and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 820.
8. D. L. JOHNSTON and W. D. HORROCKS (Jr.), *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 687.
9. R. L. DUTTA and A. K. SARKAR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* (submitted for publication)
10. T. CURTIUS and K. HEIDENREICH, *Chem. Ber.*, 1894, **27**, 55.
11. J. MC CARTHY, R. J. HOVEY and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **20**, 5821.
12. K. UENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 998.
13. G. R. BURNS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 277.
14. M. AKBAR ALI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1785.
15. M. F. ISKANDER and L. EL. SAYED., *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **16**, 147.
16. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
17. R. L. DUTTA and A. M. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 417.
18. P. RAY, *Chem. Revs.*, 1961, **61**, 318.

Schiff Base Complexes of Some Transition Metals

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SCHIFF bases have been widely used as complexing agents¹⁻³. In the present communication, N-9-anthracylidene-*p*-dimethylaminoaniline (abbreviated as ADAA) has been used to isolate and characterise the chelate compounds of Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV), Th(IV), Ni(II) and Co(II).

Experimental

The method of Kronke and Gross⁴ was employed to prepare the Schiff base N-9-anthracylidene-*p*-dimethylaminoaniline by condensing 9-anthraceneyl glyoxal hydrate and *p*-dimethylaminoaniline in ethanolic medium, m.p. 78° (Found: C, 81.24; H, 5.46; N, 7.84; requires: C, 81.80; H, 5.68; N, 7.93 per cent). All the metal salts TiCl₄, ZrCl₄, HfCl₄, ThCl₄, Ni(NO₃)₂, Ni(NCS)₂, Co(NO₃)₂ and Co(NCS)₂ used were of A. R. quality.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were carried out at the Microanalytical Laboratory, I.I.T., Kanpur. The conductance, magnetic and spectral studies were carried out by the reported methods¹⁻³. Electronic spectra were studied both in solid state and in solution in acetone.

Isolation of Complexes :

Coloured solutions obtained on mixing equimolar solutions of the metal salts and the ligand in ethanol in stoichiometric ratio 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) were refluxed for 2.5-5.5 hr on steam bath. The reaction mixtures were cooled by refrigeration for few hours to few days and coloured crystals of the complexes were obtained which were washed with water, ethanol, ether and methylcyanide and dried in vacuum desiccator.

Analytical data, colour and physical properties of the complexes are cited in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV), Th(IV), Ni(II) and Co(II) form 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complexes. All these complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in the organic solvents such as DMSO, DMF, NM, bromoform and benzene. Molar conductance measurements indicate that Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes are non-electrolytic in nature⁶ whereas the other complexes exhibit biunivalent electrolytic

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NOTES

TABLE I—COLOUR, ANALYTICAL, DATA AND PROPERTIES OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Compound	Colour	%Elemental Analysis					Molar Conductance λ_m ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹ (in NM)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molecular weight (in Bromoform)	
			Calcd. (Found) C	Calcd. (Found) H	Calcd. (Found) N	Calcd. (Found) Halogen	Calcd. (Found) Metal			Calcd.	Found
1.	[Ti(C ₂ , ₄ H ₂ , ₀ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	Violet	64.43 (64.00)	4.47 (4.23)	6.26 (6.10)	15.89 (15.02)	5.36 (5.18)	175	0.11	894	875
2.	[Zr(C ₂ , ₄ H ₂ , ₀ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	Blue	61.46 (61.08)	4.26 (4.19)	5.97 (5.78)	15.16 (15.00)	9.73 (9.68)	160	0.18	937	918
3.	[Hf(C ₂ , ₄ H ₂ , ₀ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	Pink	52.96 (52.78)	3.90 (3.75)	5.46 (5.37)	13.06 (12.82)	17.44 (17.16)	182	0.22	918	902
4.	[Th(C ₂ , ₄ H ₂ , ₀ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	Violet	52.90 (52.00)	3.68 (3.59)	5.15 (5.00)	13.04 (12.95)	21.04 (20.85)	158	0.28	1078	1056
5.	[Ni(C ₂ , ₄ H ₂ , ₀ N ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Bluish Green	66.95 (66.52)	4.51 (4.40)	9.47 (9.28)	—	6.62 (6.59)	50	2.72	886.7	872
6.	[Ni(C ₂ , ₄ H ₂ , ₀ N ₂ O) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Green	68.26 (68.00)	4.55 (4.42)	9.55 (9.36)	—	6.68 (6.59)	32	2.69	878.7	868
7.	[Co(C ₂ , ₄ H ₂ , ₀ N ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Pink	66.94 (66.49)	4.51 (4.42)	9.47 (9.51)	—	6.62 (6.56)	35	3.96	886.9	860
8.	[Co(C ₂ , ₄ H ₂ , ₀ N ₂ O) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Violet	68.24 (68.00)	4.55 (4.46)	9.55 (9.44)	—	6.68 (6.60)	28	4.02	878.9	870

nature^{7,8}. Molecular weights determined by cryoscopic method using bromoform as the solvent are in good agreement with the calculated values.

Magnetic Studies :

Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV) and Th(IV) complexes exhibit feeble paramagnetism (Table I). Nitrate and thiocyanate complexes of Ni(II) and Co(II) show magnetic moments (Table I) which are slightly lower than those usually for high spin octahedral complexes of Ni(II) and Co(II). A distortion from O_h symmetry is suggested; this is further confirmed by the electronic spectral studies.

Electronic Spectral Studies :

The electronic spectra of Ni(C₂,₄H₂,₀N₂O)₂(NO₃)₂ and Ni(C₂,₄H₂,₀N₂O)₂(NCS)₂ show bands at 9600, 12550, 17400, 29000 cm⁻¹ and 8150, 12200, 15020, 26260 cm⁻¹ respectively in solution whereas spectra in solid state exhibit peaks at 9560, 12510, 17385, 29100 cm⁻¹ and 8125, 12190, 15000, 26400 cm⁻¹ showing a close agreement. First two bands in each case may be due to the splitting of V₁ band because of the low symmetry of the ligand field transition whereas the last two bands characterise O_h symmetry.

The ratios ν_2/ν_1 for these complexes are 1.82 which are greater than the usual range 1.5-1.76 as reported⁹ for the O_h symmetry, indicating thereby tetragonal distortion from O_h symmetry.

The difference of ($\nu_3 - \nu_2$) calcd. and ($\nu_3 - \nu_2$) obs. for octahedral symmetry is small but here this difference appears to be 6302 cm⁻¹ and 6789 cm⁻¹. This difference is comparable to tetragonally distorted octahedral complexes¹¹.

The values of B calculated for the present complexes are 1173 cm⁻¹ and 1122 cm⁻¹ which are greater than the free ion value 1080 cm⁻¹. It may be assumed due to tetragonal distortion¹¹ of octahedral symmetry.

On the basis of the above facts it is concluded that the bands at 12550 cm⁻¹ and 12200 cm⁻¹ as experimentally observed are the low symmetry components. Therefore, for tetragonally distorted octahedral complexes with nitrate and thiocyanate ligands coordinated along Z-axis, the most favourable transitions for the first two bands are ³B_{1g} → ³E_g (9600 cm⁻¹, 8150 cm⁻¹) and ³B_{1g} → ³B_{2g} (12550 cm⁻¹, 12200 cm⁻¹) having energies 10 D_q - $\frac{35}{4}$ Dt and 10D_q^E in terms of radial parameters. The parameter Dt directly related to tetragonal distortion comes out to be 337 cm⁻¹ and 463 cm⁻¹. The field along Z-axis is much weaker than along the xy plane as revealed by the parameters D_q(x,y), 1255 cm⁻¹, 1200 cm⁻¹ and D_q(z), 295 cm⁻¹, 405 cm⁻¹, supporting thereby the reduced values of magnetic moments.

In the electronic spectra of Co(II) complexes in solution in acetone three bands at 8400, 8050 cm⁻¹ ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν_1); 11850, 18600 cm⁻¹ ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν_2) and 24700, 24500 cm⁻¹ ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν_3) have been observed whereas the calculated band positions (ν_2) are 19100 cm⁻¹ and 18737 cm⁻¹ respectively which are in close agreement with the experimental band positions. It may be taken as a measure of tetragonal distortion¹¹⁻¹³ of O_h symmetry. Spectral bands of these two complexes in solid state appeared at 8350, 8125 cm⁻¹; 18760, 18500 cm⁻¹ and 24670, 24420 cm⁻¹ which are identical to those as observed in solution state.

Splitting energy parameter ($10 D_q$), Racah parameter B and nephelauxetic ratio β of Co(II) complexes are 9830, 9408 cm^{-1} ; 1024, 980 cm^{-1} and 0.91, 0.87 respectively. Nephelauxetic ratio β happening due to the partial overlapping of 3d orbitals with orbitals of the ligand consists of both $f^2\sigma$ and $f^2\pi$, i.e. $f^2 = f^2\sigma + f^2\pi$ and are 0.91 and 0.87, showing thereby the coincidence to the values as have been observed for tetragonally distorted^{1,4} octahedral complexes of Co(II).

Infrared Spectral Studies :

I.R. spectra of the complexes as compared to that of the ligand show lowering of stretching frequencies of active carbonyl ($=C=O$) and azomethine ($-CH=N-$) groups such as 1700 cm^{-1} to 1630-1650 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} to 1520-1560 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating the formation of complexes through these groups. Appearance of bands at 425-465 cm^{-1} and 475-550 cm^{-1} indicate the formation of metal-oxygen (M-O) and metal-nitrogen (M-N) bonds, supporting thereby chelation through oxygen and nitrogen atoms. However, peaks around 325-425 cm^{-1} are observed in the i.r. spectra of complexes of Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV) and Th(IV), thus revealing the formation of metal-halogen (M-Cl) bonds.

The nitrate complexes of Ni(II) and Co(II) exhibit bands at 1290 cm^{-1} and 1280 cm^{-1} in their i.r. spectra, showing thereby that the complexes are nitrate-bonded^{1,5}.

The present thiocyanate complexes show i.r. bands at 2040, 2045 cm^{-1} and 800, 825 cm^{-1} indicating the coordination of thiocyanate ion with the metal ions through N-atom^{1,6}.

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References

1. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, B. P. SINGH and R. P. MAHESH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 734.
2. K. DEY and K. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 261.
3. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, B. P. SINGH, R. L. GOEL and R. P. MAHESH, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, **45**, 137.
4. F. KRONKE and K. F. GROSS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, **92**, 36.
5. M. P. TROTIA, D. K. RASTOGI and W. U. MALIK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 340.
6. C. M. HARRIS and E. D. MCKENZIE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 407.
7. N. S. GILL and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3997.

8. D. K. RASTOGI and K. C. SHARMA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 2220.
9. D. K. RASTOGI and K. C. SHARMA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 2222.
10. O. BOSTRUP and C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1957, **11**, 1223.
11. A. B. P. LEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 1042.
12. G. R. BURE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 277.
13. B. SINGH and U. AGRAWAL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 2341.
14. D. K. RASTOGI and K. C. SHARMA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 2225.
15. B. M. GATEHOUSE, S. E. LIVINGSTONE and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, **8**, 75.
16. J. L. BURMEISTER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, **3**, 225.

Mn(II) and Cd(II) Complexes of Dicyandiamide

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As a part of our programme of investigation on amide complexes of divalent metal ions, we have reported^{1,2} complexes of lactams and nicotinamide. Dicyandiamide aroused our interest as it does not contain an oxygen donor atom even though four possible bonding sites are present. As a result, this communication reports a number of complexes of Mn(II) and Cd(II) with dicyandiamide.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. Absolute ethanol solution of metal salts were reacted with ethanolic dicyandiamide solution in 1:2 proportion. On shaking compounds separated out in some cases, while in other cases compounds were precipitated after refluxing the solution for thirty minutes and keeping overnight.

Metal and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution of the compounds. Magnetic moments of Mn(II) complexes were measured by Gouy method. I.R. spectra were recorded in nujol mulls using Unicam Sp-200 and electronic spectra by Unicam Sp-500 spectrophotometers with reflectance attachment. Relevant data are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Conductance values of the compounds in acetone solution are low indicating non-electrolytic nature, except for the perchlorate complex which has $\Delta\Lambda$ value ~ 250 mhos. cm^2 suggesting 1:2 electrolytic